

Academic Personnel Management: Implications on Goals Achievement and Administrative Effectiveness in Public Universities in South West, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out on academic personnel management and its implications on goals management achievement and administrative effectiveness in public Nigerian universities in South West, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised universities lecturers in South West region of Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Three Hundred [300] respondents, selected from six universities, one from each of the six states [Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Ogun, Lagos and Ekiti] in South West region of Nigeria. From each state, Fifty [50] respondents, were selected, through a simple random sampling technique. Three [3] research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study. A self-structured and developed research instrument titled, "Questionnaire on Academic Personnel Management: Implications on Administrative Effectiveness in Public Universities in South West, Nigeria", fashioned on a four Likert rating scale of Strongly Agreed [SA] Agreed [A], Disagreed [D], and Strongly Disagreed [SD] rated on 4:3;2 and 1, respectively. The instrument was validated by an expert in test and measurement while its reliability was determined through a test-retest method at two-week intervals. A 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. Descriptive statistics [simple percentages, frequency counts and mean] were used to analyze the data generated. Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were made that welfare services, and in-service training could enhance academic personnel commitment and pedagogical skills towards achieving organizational goals, while motivation had no significant influence. Based on the conclusions, recommendations were made that government should intensify efforts to improve academic welfare services; supports should be given to them to embark on in-service training.

Key words: Personnel, Management, Goals achievement, Administrative effectiveness, Public Universities

Background to the Study

Administration is a cardinal factor that can lead to or mar achieving or not of the set but goals and objectives of any organization, educational organization, inclusively. In any educational sector, imparting skills, values and knowledge are the focus and targets to achieve all these huge on human factors or personnel within the system in terms of their commitment to job, motivation to work, quantity and quality, and a host of others. Oyekan (2004) stressed that school personnel are the bedrock on which the whole of the school is built in terms of standard, quality service delivery, administration and management effectiveness. Thus, the place school staff or personnel management not be over emphasized and overlook in school system.

Personnel management can be expressed as that part of the management task which is concerned with the human resources in organization and their contribution to its effectiveness (Edem, 2006). In the context of this research the focus is strictly on academic personnel management. Oyekan (2004) strongly asserted that to achieve academic excellence is a function teachers also educational growth and development to a large extent depends on teachers.

Day (2015), further noted that teachers or academic personnel management is imperative to acquisition of skills, values and knowledge. Teachers should also be involving in some activities of the school and not only imparting knowledge to the learners. Also they should be involving in planning of educational activities or overall administrative effectiveness of the school. In the school system, the Ministry of Education is the employer, while the employees are

the teachers (academic personnel). The staff needs must be satisfied and the employers also have their own goals and objectives to achieve in organization. In a nutshell, the objectives of school may be very difficult to be achieved without teacher's contributions to the system.

Kizlik (2021), stated that for teachers to contribute maximally and optimally to schools administration or as dispensers of knowledge demand proper management in terms of coordinations, towards achieving the school set goals. Thus, Teachers management becomes very important in order to acquire schools vision and mission statements (Oyekan 2004)

Oyekan (2004), stated also that teachings is a living profession therefore, teacher should be allowed to be participating in in-service training programmes, workshops, conferences that are related to their work so that they can be upgrading and updating their pedagogical skills for effective job delivery and performance. Day (2015), maintained that in a service training is a process by which teachers renew, review and extend their commitment of change agents to the moral purposes of teaching and by which they acquire and develop knowledge, skill and values through each phrase of their teaching lives. Teachers should within the school settings be involving in planning school activities, their inputs in no doubt will not only enhance academic activities but also, improved administration of the school which will culminate into achieving school set goals and objectives.

As observed by researchers, several researches globally have identified have qualified teachers as bed rocks and pillars which schools are built on. However, from the avalanche of researchers much have not been focused or conducted on academic personnel management:

Implications on goal achievement and administrative effectiveness in public universities in South West, Nigeria. This identified gap therefore, motivated the researchers to carry out the study

Statement of the study

Effective management of personnel in any organization is a key to success of the organisation in terms of achieving its set out goals. However, in the contexts of school organization academic personnel roles mainly are to impart values, skills and knowledge. Although, they are activities administratively which they can also carry out. However, this depends on well they are managed by their employers. It was against this foregoing background this study was carried but by the researchers on academic personal management and its implication on goals achievement and administrative effectiveness in public universities in South West Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of the study was on academic personnel management and its implications on goals achievement and administrative effectiveness in public universities in South West Nigeria.

The specific objectives were to:

- i. ascertain the impact of welfare services in academic staff commitment to goals achievement in public universities in South West, Nigeria.
- ii. determine the influence of motivation of academic personnel and service delivery in public universities in South West, Nigeria; and

- iii. establish influence of in-service training in academic personal pedagogical skills development in South West, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

Three research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study. They were:

- i. Can welfare service enhance academic personnel commitment to goals achievement in public universities in South West Nigeria?
- ii. Will motivation improve services teaching among academic personal in public universities in South West Nigeria?
- iii. Can in-service training program improve academic personnel pedagogical skills development in public universities in South West, Nigeria?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised, lecturers from public universities in South West region in Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Three hundred (300) respondents that were selected from six universities in South West region states in Nigeria (Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Lagos Osun and Ekiti). From each of the states one public university was selected in which Fifty (50) respondents were selected through, a simple random sampling technique. The universities were:

1. Adekunle Ajasin university (AAU), Ondo State
2. University of Lagos, Lagos State
3. Tai-Solarin University of Education, Ogun State
4. Osun state University, Osun State

5. University of Ibadan, Oyo State
6. Ekiti State University, Ekiti State

Three research questions were raised to guide the study. A self-structured and developed research instruments titled, “Questionnaires on Academic Personnel Management: Implications on Goals Achievement and Administrative Effectiveness in Public Universities in South West, Nigeria”. It was fashioned on four likert rating scale of strongly Agreed (SA) Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4: 3: 2 and 1, respectively.

The research instruments were validated by an expert in Test and Measurement while, it reliability was obtained through test –retest method at two weeks interval and 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data obtained were analyzed using, descriptive statistics (simple percentages frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}))

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Findings

Research Question One: Can welfare services enhance academic staff commitment to goals achievement in public universities in South West, Nigeria?

Table 1: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on can welfare services enhance academic staff commitment to goals achievement in public universities in South West, Nigeria.

		N=300				C=2.5		
SN	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1.	Will free health services encourage you to work well?	256 85.33	23 7.66	12 4	9 3	300	3.75	Accepted
2.	Free health service will not determine whether, I will work better or not.	17 5.66	11 3.66	29 9.66	243 81	300	1.34	Rejected

3.	Living at staff residence will make me to be regular and punctual at work place.	249 83	32 10.66	17 5.66	2 0.66	300	3.76	Accepted
4.	Even if I am living at staff residence, I may still not be regular and punctual at work place.	13 4.33	16 5.33	239 79.66	32 10.66	300	2.03	Rejected
5.	Free transportation will make me to always come for work.	259 86.33	13 4.33	7 2.33	21 7	300	3.7	Accepted
6.	Without free transportation, I am always be at my work place.	3 1	9 3	11 3.66	277 92.33	300	1.26	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	797 44.27	104 5.77	315 17.5	584 32.44		2.64	Accepted

Keys:

T = Total Number of Respondent, C = cut off point, (\bar{x}) = Mean, SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD= Strongly Disagreed.

Source - Field Source, (2025).

Table 1, above presents the findings on research question one. On item [1] the following responses 256 {83.33}, 23 {7.66}, 12 {4} and 9 {3} for were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item [2] 17 [5.66], 11 [3.66], 29 [9.66] and 243 {81} were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item {3}, 249 [83], 32 [10.66], 17 [5.66] and 2 [0.66] were got for strongly agreed, agreed disagreed and strongly disagreed, also

On item (4), the following were got as well: 13 (4.33) 16 [5.33] 239 [79.66] and 32 [10.66] for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item [5], responses got were as follows: 259 [86.33], 13 [4.33], 7 [2.33] and 21 [7] for strongly agreed, agreed, agreed, disagreed, respectively.

Finally, 3 [1], 9 [3], 11 [3.66] and 277 [92.33] were obtained as response for strongly agreed, agreed disagreed, respectively.

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Generally speaking, the total weight of the findings indicated that, the average rating scale of four $\{\bar{x} = 2.5\}$ was lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four $\{\bar{x} = 2.64\}$ thus portends that welfare services could enhance staff commitment to goals achievement in public universities in South West, Nigeria.

Research Questions Two: Will motivation improve service delivery among academic personnel in public universities in South West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Showing simple percentages frequency counts and mean $\{x\}$ on will motivation improve service delivery among academic personnel in public universities in South West, Nigeria.

		N=300				C=2.5		
S\N	Item	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Decisions
7.	Prompt payment of salary will boost my energy to work	49 16.33	236 78.66	9 3	6 2	300	3.09	Accepted
8.	If my salary is not timely paid, I may not work to the best of my ability.	19 6.33	22 7.33	33 11	226 75.33	300	1.44	Rejected
9.	Payment of allowances and annual leave bones will induce my interest to render good job.	246 82	30 10	5 11.66	19 6.33	300	3.67	Accepted
10.	I am always discouraging to work, if my allowances are not paid.	9 3	5 18.66	31 10.33	255 85	300	1.22	Rejected
11.	Timely promotion is a factor that gingers me to be productive.	189 63	56 18.66	33 11	22 7.33	300	3.37	Accepted
12.	I will never be productive whenever, I am denied of promotion.	3 1	2 0.66	266 88.66	29 9.66	300	1.93	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	515 28.61	351 19.5	377 20.94	557 30.94		2.45	Rejected

Keys:

T = Total Number of Respondent, C = cut off point, (\bar{x}) = Mean, SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD= Strongly Disagreed.

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Table 2, above showed the findings on research question two on item (7), 49(16.33), 236(78.66), 9(3) and 6(2) were got for strongly agreed, agreed disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively on items (8), the follows responses were also got; 19 (6.33), 22(7.33), 33 (11) and 226(75.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, on item ,(9) responses obtained were 246 (82), 30(10), 5 (1.66),and 19(6.33), for strongly agreed, agreed ,disagreed and strongly disagreed .

Item (10) showed 9(3), 5 (1.66), 31 (10.33) and 255 (85) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (11), responses got were 189(63), 56 (18.66), 33(11), 22 (7.23) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed respectively. On item (11), the following responses were also got; 189 (63), 56 (18.66), 33 (11), and 22(7.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (12) responses were 3(1} 2 (0.66}, 266 (88.66} and 29 (9.66} for strongly agree, agree disagreed and strongly disagreed.

However, the total weight of the finding indicated that the average rating scale of four(\bar{x} =2.5) was greater than the mean of average rating scale of four (\bar{x} = 2. 45). This implies that motivation had no significant influence on service delivery among the academic personnel in public universities in South West Nigerian of the nation

Research Question Three: Can in search training programme improve academic personnel pedagogical skill in public universities in South West, Nigeria?

Table 3: Showing simple percentage’s frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on can in-service training programme improve academic personnel pedagogical skill in public universities South West Nigeria

		N= 300				C= 2.5		
S/N	ITEM	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
13	Participating in workshops will	258	34	3	5	300	3.81	Accepted

	improve my ability to control class during teaching	86	11.33	1	1.66			
14	Participating in workshops cannot improve my ability to control class during teaching	23 7.66	23 7.66	35 11.66	219 73	300	1.5	Rejected
15	Conference participation can enhance my versatility in using teaching techniques	241 80.33	44 14.66	6 2	9 3	300	3.72	Accepted
16	My job skills cannot be enhanced despite am attending conferences	1 0.33	11 3.66	255 85	33 11	300	1.93	Rejected
17	Participating in seminars will expose me to different evaluation methods	244 81.33	28 9.33	17 5.66	11 3.66	300	3.68	Accepted
18	Participation in seminar have nothing to do with my exposure to different evaluation methods	11 3.66	11 3.66	49 16.33	229 76.33	300	1.34	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	778 43.22	151 8.38	365 20.27	506 28.11		2.66	Accepted

T = Total Number of Respondent, C = cut off point, (\bar{x}) = Mean, SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD= Strongly Disagreed.

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Table 3, above showed the findings on research question three. On item (13), responses got were 258(86), 34(11.33), 3(1) and 5(1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (14), 23(7.66), 35(11.66) and 219(73) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed were obtained. On item (15) responses obtained indicated the following; 241(80.33), 44(14.66), 6(2) and 9(3) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed.

On item (17), the following responses were got as well; 244(81.33), 28(9.33), 17(5.66) and 11(3.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed, respectively. On

item (18), 11(3.66), 11(3.66), 49(16.33) and 229(76.33) were got as responses for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed.

The total weight of the findings however, indicated that the average rating scale of form ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) was lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.6$) thus, means that in-services framing could significantly improve academic personnel pedagogical skills in public university in South West, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The findings on research question one aligns with the opinion of Wokoma and Obasi (2023), since they both maintained their welfare packages have profound impact on the employees job satisfaction. Further, that it gives employees a sense of security and well-being which can alleviate stress, and promote commitment to organizational goals achievement. In the same spirit, Olulube (2019), maintained that employees that feel supported with good welfare packages they are more likely to have interest their jobs and be working assiduously towards achieving organizational set out goals and objectives.

Also, the findings on research question two is in sharp contrast with two opinion of several scholars like Stephen and Mauthe (2014) in Akintoye and Afobruku (2022) that, staff motivation has a significant impact on employee performance. Also, it negates the position of Okunre (2010) and poi(2020) that an organisation that genuinely cares about its employees well-being will be concerned with creating a position work environment in which individuals will recognize that they are valued, which in turn will boost their performance.

The findings on research question three was corroborated by Nakpodia (2018), that in-service training is a channel through which teachers can acquire more conceptual and technical knowledge, skills and competencies in their teaching subjects and pedagogy in order to improve their efficiency in the classroom. This also aligns with the stance of Clotfeller (2005) that in-service training will enable teacher to acquire new knowledge, develop new skills improve competencies and so on.

Conclusion

Based on the result of the study conclusions were made that staff welfare packages could enhance or improve academic personnel commitment towards goals achievement and administrative effectiveness in public university in South West, Nigeria. However, motivation of academic personnel have no significance influence on academic personnel service delivery while, in-service training programme could result into an improvement of pedagogical skills improvement among academic personnel in South West, Nigeria in public universities in contemporary Nigerian society.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the research or study the following recommendations were made;

1. Efforts should be intensify by government to more improve welfare service package for academic staff in public universities, specifically in Nigeria.
2. University personnel should be encouraged to be attending or involving in in-service training programmes on continual basis

3. Academic personnel should be given supports in all forms towards their participation in-service training programmes.
4. Apart from regular payment of salary, the results shows that it has no much influence on service delivery other incentives should be given to academic staff of public universities in Nigeria
5. The academic personnel in public universities in Nigeria should be given priority and fair treatment by the universities management in Nigeria
6. Academic personnel in Nigerian universities should be given opportunity to advance or make their grievances on issues affecting their jobs known to the management, and so on.

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